

Photoactivation of Color Centers Induced by CW Laser Irradiation in Ion-Implanted Diamond

Vanna Pugliese, Elena Nieto Hernández,* Emilio Corte, Marco Govoni, Sviatoslav Ditalia Tchernij, Paolo Olivero, and Jacopo Forneris

Cite This: *ACS Photonics* 2025, 12, 3803–3814

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ABSTRACT: Split-vacancy color centers in diamonds are promising solid-state platforms for the implementation of photonic quantum technologies. These luminescent defects are commonly fabricated upon low-energy ion implantation and subsequent thermal annealing. Their technological uptake will require the availability of reliable methods for the controlled, large-scale production of localized individual photon emitters. This task is partially achieved by controlled ion implantation to introduce selected impurities in the host material and requires the development of challenging beam focusing or collimation procedures coupled with single-ion detection techniques. We report on the protocol for the direct optical activation of split-vacancy color centers in diamond via localized processing with a continuous-wave laser at mW optical powers. We demonstrate the activation of photoluminescent Mg- and Sn-related centers at both the ensemble and single-photon emitter levels in ion-implanted, high-purity diamond crystals without further thermal processing. The proposed lithographic method enables the activation of individual color centers at specific positions of a large-area sample by means of a relatively inexpensive equipment offering real-time, in situ monitoring of the process.

KEYWORDS: color centers, split-vacancy, single-photon, diamond, ion implantation, laser activation

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INTRODUCTION

Color centers in diamond represent promising platforms for the implementation of quantum technologies.^{1–3} Their capability to generate single photons on demand represents a viable tool for realizing high-density photonic platforms operating at room temperature.^{4,5} Among the known single-photon emitters (SPEs) in diamond, the negatively charged nitrogen-vacancy (NV⁻) center,^{6–8} offers enticing applications in the field of quantum sensing and metrology in virtue of its outstanding optically addressable spin properties at room temperature^{9,10} and its sensitivity to external electromagnetic fields.^{11,12} The latter feature, combined with a low Debye–Waller factor and a long radiative lifetime, could nevertheless represent a significant drawback for other specific applications in the framework of quantum technologies, in which the generation of indistinguishable photons at a high rate is required.^{1,13} Various alternative color centers have therefore drawn increasing attention in the past few years, including the group-IV related defects (also known as G4 V color centers)^{14–18} and the magnesium-vacancy emitter.¹⁹ These systems, all of which are based on the split-vacancy structural configuration, display substantially better properties in terms of zero-phonon line (ZPL) emission line width, Debye–Waller factor, and emission rate, and they offer lower environmental

sensitivity in addition to energy level configurations that allow the implementation of coherent control schemes.^{4,20}

In particular, this work focuses on the formation of two of the aforementioned luminescent defects in diamond, namely, the negative charge state of the tin-vacancy (SnV)^{21,22} and magnesium-vacancy (MgV) defect complexes.¹⁹ The SnV⁻ center has emerged as an important quantum platform in the field of quantum communication due to its long coherence time, even at relatively high temperatures.^{15,23} On the other hand, the MgV⁻ center is a newly discovered emitter that holds substantial potential for implementation in quantum sensing and photonics.^{19,24} Understanding the dynamics related to the formation and activation of these defects is therefore of crucial importance for fully exploiting their quantum-optophysical properties in quantum technologies.

To date, the most widely employed method for creating defects in diamond is based on ion implantation followed by a high-temperature annealing to promote the formation of stable

Received: April 10, 2025

Revised: June 13, 2025

Accepted: June 13, 2025

Published: July 1, 2025

Figure 1. (a) PL map of the array of spots activated in MgH^- -implanted diamond upon 405 nm laser processing at varying conditions of optical power and exposure time. (b) Emission spectrum, background-subtracted, and normalized to first-order Raman peak, of the spot circled in white in (a) processed for 75 min at a 25 mW optical power. The inset (orange) displays the PL spectrum acquired from a region of the sample implanted with MgH^- ions that did not undergo laser processing. (c) Emission intensity of the MgV^- ZPL as a function of the laser processing optical power for exposure times of 1 min (gray) and 75 min (red). (d) Emission intensity of the MgV^- ZPL as a function of the laser processing time under 1 mW (gray) and 25 mW (red) optical powers.

defects in the desired structural configuration.^{25–28} This procedure enables a precise control of the location and quantity of impurities introduced into the diamond substrate.^{29–31} However, the defect formation efficiency (defined as the ratio between the areal density of optically active color centers generated by ion implantation and ion fluence in an undoped substrate) after conventional thermal annealing has been reported to be critically low, i.e., not exceeding 5 and 8% for SnV^- and MgV^- optically active charge states, respectively.³²

Interestingly, recent emission channeling experiments have determined that the structural formation efficiency, i.e., the fraction of implanted ions resulting in a bond-centered configuration in the diamond lattice, exceeds 30% for both Sn^- ³³ and Mg -containing defects¹⁹ in as-implanted samples, i.e., before any thermal processing stage. This observation is compatible with the split-vacancy configuration of the MgV and SnV defect complexes, although at the state of the art, it is not fully understood how probable the formation of the defect in such configuration with respect to other possible defect arrangements based on the incorporation of one (or more)

lattice vacancies. Nevertheless, the formation of split-vacancy centers at a far-from-negligible concentration can be hypothesized. The fact that such emitters are largely inactive in as-implanted samples suggests that the formation of photon-emitting color centers requires a further processing step, functional to the stabilization of the electronic configuration of the defect in the desired optically active state.

This work explores the optical activation of MgV^- and Sn -related (photoluminescence (PL) emission at 595 nm in Sn -implanted diamond^{34,21}) optically active color centers in diamond straight after ion implantation (“as-implanted”, in the following), i.e., without any postimplantation thermal treatment. The protocol discussed here relies on the localized activation of color centers using a continuous-wave (CW) laser with mW power, providing a different mechanism with respect to previously reported femtosecond-laser annealing studies.^{35–38} This simple and accessible process enables stable in situ activation of color centers through exposure to conventional and widely available instrumentation. This arrangement is not only convenient due to the use of the same setup used for optical characterization but also provides insights into the

Figure 2. (a) PL map of the array of spots activated in Sn^- -implanted diamond upon 405 nm laser processing at varying conditions of optical power and exposure time. (b) Emission spectrum, background-subtracted, and normalized to the first-order Raman peak, of the spot circled in white in (a) processed for 75 min at a 25 mW optical power. The inset (orange) displays the PL spectrum acquired from a region of sample implanted with Sn^- ions which did not undergo laser processing. (c) Emission intensity of the 595 nm ZPL as a function of the laser processing optical power for exposure times of 1 min (gray) and 75 min (red). (d) Emission intensity of the 595 nm ZPL as a function of the laser processing time under 2.5 mW (gray) and 25 mW (red) optical powers.

mechanisms that determine the optical activation of color centers and their formation.

RESULTS

Laser Processing. The experiments were performed on two high-purity diamond samples, $2 \times 2 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^3$ sized IIa-type, single-crystal diamond plates produced by ElementSix by chemical vapor deposition synthesis. The first sample (referred to as “Sample A” in the following) was implanted with MgH^{13} ions at an energy of 80 keV and an ion fluence of $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The second sample (“Sample B” in the following) was implanted with Sn^- ions at an energy of 56 keV and a fluence of $1 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The fluence values were selected to replicate the conditions leading to the formation of high-density ensembles of color centers upon standard activation processes.^{19,21,25} The discrepancy between the two fluences was meant to compensate for the mass difference between the two accelerated ions, therefore limiting the ion-induced damage in the case of Sn. The surfaces of both samples were untreated, i.e., no specific surface termination was induced by means of chemical or plasma processes, either preliminarily or subsequently to the ion implantation process.

The as-implanted samples were characterized in a custom-fiber-coupled confocal microscope. A 522 nm diode laser (referred to as a “probing laser” in the following) with a fixed optical power of $100 \mu\text{W}$ was focused on the sample surface in the photoluminescence (PL) mapping and spectral analysis. The optical power reported above was low enough to avoid giving rise to any photoactivation effects. This was verified by monitoring the PL intensity for a duration exceeding the time scale of both the spectral and the PL mapping measurements (see Supporting Information S1—PL count rate stability). In the spectral characterization, an integration time of 20 s was used per frame with a total number of frames of 5 (100 s). While the laser exposure during a PL scan acquisition time (~ 1 s) was given by a dwell time of 20 ms per pixel ($180 \times 180 \text{ nm}^2$), multiplied by the number of pixels required to cover a diffraction-limited area ($\sim 0.1 \mu\text{m}^2$). The photoactivation of MgV^- and Sn-related emission in as-implanted samples was studied as a function of the wavelength of the laser beams adopted for substrate processing. To this purpose, three continuous-wave (CW) lasers (referred to as “processing” lasers) emitting at 405, 445, and 522 nm wavelengths were employed in a “high” (i.e., 0.1–25 mW) power range. Processing and probing lasers were combined with a long-

pass dichroic mirror (520 nm cutoff wavelength), allowing a simultaneous irradiation of the substrates.

The investigation involved the analysis of the dependence of photoactivation on the optical power and duration of the laser exposure for each considered activation wavelength. To this aim, a systematic study of the implanted samples was performed by defining, for each processing-laser wavelength, a regular grid of spots processed with different laser irradiation parameters at varying optical powers (i.e., 8 values in the 0.1–25 mW range) and exposure times (i.e., 6 values ranging from 1 to 75 min). This arrangement allowed us to assess the dependence of the photoactivation efficiency as a function of the energy delivered to the sample via the processing-laser irradiation. Additionally, a longer irradiation (10 h) was performed at the maximum available power for each activation wavelength to identify the asymptotic behavior of the photoactivation process.

For each of the irradiated grids, a PL map was acquired before and after the processing-laser irradiation. A spectral analysis was carried out for each irradiated spot to identify the origin of the PL emission. The spectral range considered for the study of the MgV^- and the Sn-related defects was 550–650 and 580–680 nm, respectively. In both cases, the spectra were processed by a background PL subtraction with respect to the PL collected from an unirradiated area of the samples and were normalized to the first-order Raman peak intensity for the sake of consistency, in consideration of possible slight variations in probing-laser focusing conditions.

Effects of Exposure Time and Laser Irradiation Power. Two exemplary results are reported in Figures 1 and 2 for the photoactivation of MgV^- and Sn-related centers, respectively, under 405 nm processing-laser irradiation. Figures 1a and 2a show the PL maps acquired in implanted diamond following the patterning of a grid of regularly spaced spots under different optical powers (increasing across rows) and exposure times (increasing across columns). The processed spots are associated with an increase in the PL emission intensity with respect to the background, unequivocally indicating the local activation of color centers. A systematic analysis of the spectral emission from each activated spot (Figures 1b and 2b) evidenced the signature of specific color centers, namely, the MgV^- center in Sample A, denoted by a sharp ZPL at 557.4 nm, and the 595 nm Sn-related peak in Sample B.^{21,34} By contrast, the background emission acquired from the implanted, untreated region surrounding the laser spots (orange lines in Figures 1b and 2b) evidenced the lack of those signatures and the sole presence of the first-order Raman peak at the 1332 cm^{-1} wavenumber shift.

The PL emission rate was found to increase in both samples with the optical power of the processing laser, indicating a clear correlation between sample exposure and activation yield of color centers. This correlation relation can be appreciated in Figures 1c and 2c, where the area underlying the emission spectra profiles in the 550–650 and 580–680 nm range for the MgV^- and Sn-related emission is plotted against the 405 nm processing optical power for the two limit exposure times (1 and 75 min). Particularly, the data exhibit a clearly increasing trend, which is accompanied by a saturation behavior at high optical powers (i.e., >10 mW for the MgV^- center and >20 mW for the Sn-related center).

Along with the power dependence study, the dependence of the PL emission intensity on the processing-laser exposure time was investigated for each of the considered optical

powers. Figures 1d and 2d show the intensity of each activated spot (measured as the integral of the PL spectral peaks) for MgV^- and Sn-related emitters; integrative data are reported for different time exposures in the exemplary case of the 405 nm processing-laser wavelength under two different optical powers. In both cases, an increasing trend with the exposure time is observed, with the MgV^- and Sn-related emission reaching a saturation value after 30 and 50 min of processing-laser irradiation, respectively.

According to the emission channeling measurements available for Sn- and Mg-ion-implanted samples,^{19,33} we interpret the observed results as a process of laser-induced optical activation of ensembles of defects which are already available in the diamond lattice in the split-vacancy configuration, but that are configured in an electronic state which is associated with a dark state. This attribution is motivated by the fact that additional interpretations can be ruled out, as detailed in the following. First, the considered wavelengths and instantaneous optical powers are insufficient to introduce any structural modification to the diamond crystal,³⁹ or any thermal effect comparable with the typical annealing temperatures required for vacancy diffusion.⁴⁰ This latter consideration was further supported by the observation of the same activation process at cryogenic temperatures, particularly in the consideration of the very large thermal conductivity of the diamond crystal. In addition, the absence of any statistically significant Raman diamond peak variation between the laser-irradiated spots and the solely implanted area (see Supporting Information S2—comparison of diamond Raman peak), excludes the occurrence of any structural alteration of the lattice in the investigated energy regime.⁴¹ Moreover, the possible dependence of the photoactivation on surface functionalization was analyzed by performing laser processing treatments on surface oxidized reference samples (see Supporting Information S3—photoactivation in surface-functionalized diamond), leading to no apparent changes in the trend of the PL emission increase with respect to the one observed for the untreated surface sample. This test enabled us to rule out the possible attribution of the conversion process to a laser-assisted surface charge modification.^{42,43} Moreover, it is worth stressing that this latter hypothesis was further in contrast with the experimental observation of the phenomenon upon laser processing at cryogenic temperatures under vacuum conditions, at which laser-assisted surface chemistry is expected to be strongly inhibited.

MgV^- Photoactivation. In this case, we can first assume that the photoactivation of MgV^- defect complexes in the optically active MgV^- charge state is due to the conversion from a single optically inactive configuration via photon absorption. Considering the lack of GR1 emission, i.e., the PL signature of the neutral vacancy, in the as-implanted sample (see Figures 1b and 2b), the radiation-induced vacancy density generated by ion implantation is then assumed to be configured in its negative charge state (ND1 center⁴⁴), which is optically inactive in the considered spectral range (500–800 nm). This observation suggests that the Fermi level in the ion-implanted sample is located at a minimum of 3.2 eV above the valence band. In this case, the formation energy of the ND1 charge state of the vacancy is indeed more favorable with respect to the GR1 configuration.⁴⁵ This estimation of the Fermi level position in the energy gap is compatible with the doubly negative charge state (MgV^{2-}) being the favored electronic configuration of the MgV^- defect complex, on the

basis of the theoretical results obtained in ref 24. Such interpretation is consistent with the lack of observed PL from the MgV^- charge state in the as-implanted sample and is reasonable considering the introduction of overall negative charge in the material via ion implantation. The increase in the MgV^- emission upon laser processing is thus interpreted as ionization of the MgV^{2-} charge state via the transition of an electron to the conduction band.

The process described above can be modeled as follows. The total density of Mg-containing split-vacancy defects n_{SV} is given by the sum of the active and inactive configurations. Such configurations are respectively attributed to the sole MgV^- and MgV^{2-} charge states (n_1 , n_2 , respectively), i.e.:

$$n_1 + n_2 = n_{\text{SV}} \quad (1)$$

The photoinduced charge state conversion between the “1-” and “2-” configurations can be thus described by the following time-dependent rate equation:

$$\frac{dn_1(t)}{dt} = r_{21}n_2(t) - r_{12}n_1(t) \quad (2)$$

where the r_{21} (r_{12}) terms indicate the activation (deactivation) rate coefficients related to the conversion from (to) the MgV^{2-} to (from) the MgV^- configuration. By combining eqs 1 and 2 and implementing the experimental constraint $n_1(t = 0) = 0$, the expression for the density of MgV^- centers in the singly negative charge state as a function of the exposure time to the processing laser is given by

$$n_1(t) = \frac{r_{21}}{r_{21} + r_{12}} n_{\text{SV}} (1 - e^{-(r_{21} + r_{12})t}) \quad (3)$$

Here, r_{21} and r_{12} can be regarded in general as transition rates dependent on the wavelength λ and power P . The asymptotic behavior at $t \rightarrow \infty$ is indicative of the maximum fraction $r_{21}/(r_{21} + r_{12})$ of split-vacancy centers which can be converted in the MgV^- charge state.

If the photoactivation is considered as a one-photon absorption process, the transition rates can be described in simple terms as⁴⁶ $r_{21} = a_{21}(\lambda)P$ and $r_{12} = a_{12}(\lambda)P$, leading to a power-independent fraction of emitters activated in the asymptotic limit (i.e., $n_1(t \rightarrow \infty) = a_{21}/(a_{21} + a_{12})n_{\text{SV}} = An_{\text{SV}}$). Conversely, at lower time scales, the product of the CW lasing power and the exposure time enables us to describe the process in terms of the total energy E deposited within the diffraction-limited focal point of the optical objective:

$$n_1(E) = An_{\text{SV}}(1 - \exp(-(a_{21} + a_{12})E)) \quad (4)$$

Under the assumption that the physical observable of the experiment—i.e., the PL emission intensity I —is proportional to n_1 , then the dependence of the latter on the energy delivered to the sample can be assessed. It is therefore worth noting that the functional form obtained in eq 4 offers a reasonable description of the data points reported in Figure 1. The wavelength dependence of the $I(E)$ photoactivation process was investigated for the MgV^- optically active charge state by generating an array of spots under different laser processing parameters, similarly to what is presented in Figure 1a for 405 nm CW irradiation. The processing was performed with CW optical powers in the mW range at exposure times varying from 1 to 75 min, depending on the total energy deposited at each spot. A full list of the specific parameters is reported in Table 1. To prevent cross-effects with the other spots, the processes involving the highest energy deposition (corresponding to ~ 10

Table 1. Laser Processing Parameters Adopted for the Photoactivation MgV^- and Sn-Related Centers

processing-laser wavelength (nm)	processing optical power range (mW)	deposited energy range (J)
405	1.0–25.0	0.1–900.0
445	0.8–5.0	0.1–136.8
522	1.5–7.7	0.1–151.2

h of laser exposure) were fabricated on separate regions of Sample A, again with the purpose of assessing the asymptotic behavior of the photoactivation process at large deposited energies.

A confocal PL map acquired under 522 nm probing excitation is reported in Figure 3a–c for each of the arrays fabricated under 522, 445, and 405 nm. The PL intensity is encoded in the same color scale for all maps to highlight the effect of different processing wavelengths. The dependence of the PL intensity (measured as the integral of the MgV^- ZPL spectrum acquired from each processed spot) on the energy delivered to the spots is plotted in Figure 3d–f, respectively. All of the data points resulted to be distributed on the same curve independently of the specific optical power at which the processing laser was held, thus justifying the assumptions made in eq 4. These graphs report a clear dependence of the asymptotic saturation plateau at large energies with the processing wavelength. Particularly, the saturation of the PL intensity is maximum under 405 nm processing and exhibits a decreasing trend at increasing wavelength, with a saturation intensity which is more than halved under 522 nm CW irradiation. Further processing performed with a 594 nm laser (not shown here) at similar optical powers did not result in the formation of any MgV^- emitters. Therefore, it can be inferred that the photoactivation process is characterized by a threshold energy comprised between 2.09 and 2.38 eV, as schematically shown in Figure 3g.

In order to validate the photophysical model proposed in eqs 1 and 4, the data sets in Figure 3d–f were fitted according to a single-exponential function in the form $I(E) = I_0(1 - \exp(-E/\alpha))$. The fitting curve suitably accounted for the experimental data collected under 522 nm laser processing (Figure 3d), but offered unsatisfactory results for those obtained at lower wavelengths. A reasonable agreement with the data was found for the 445 and 405 nm processing wavelengths when adding a second exponential term to the fitting function, i.e.:

$$I(E) = I_0(1 - a \exp(-E/\alpha) - b \exp(-E/\beta)) \quad (5)$$

The relevant parameter I_0 , describing the fraction of emitters activated in the asymptotic limit, is listed in Table 2 for each considered processing wavelength. This quantity, which is proportional to the ionization rate of the MgV^{2-} charge state, shows a monotonic decreasing trend at increasing wavelengths, suggesting a more effective process at shorter wavelengths.

It is worth noting that the appearance of a second exponential term in the $I(E)$ curves at 445 and 405 nm is not justified in terms of nonlinear photon absorption, such as two-photon processes,^{46,47} particularly since the increase in the laser processing energy should favor one-photon ionization.⁴⁷ Conversely, here we assume the presence of an energy threshold (in the 2.38 \rightarrow 2.79 eV range, i.e., between 522 and 445 nm) enabling the interaction of the MgV^- configuration with a possible third charge state other than

Figure 3. Photoactivation dependence on the laser processing parameters for the MgV^- color center. The first row shows the confocal maps acquired on an array of spots undergone photoactivation via laser processing at (a) 522 nm, (b) 445 nm, and (c) 405 nm. The second row shows the integrated PL intensity (integral of the MgV^- ZPL spectral peak) collected spots as a function of the energy deposited on each spot under processing wavelengths of (d) 522 nm, (e) 445 nm, and (f) 405 nm. (g) Schematic representation of the energy levels of the MgV defect charge states. The negative charge state MgV^- is represented as a 2-level system in the diamond energy gap. Only the ground state of the doubly negative charge state MgV^{2-} is only under the assumption that any excited state lies above the bottom of the conduction band. The colored green arrows represent the transitions induced by the processing laser at 522 nm. The shaded blue area in the gap depicts the Fermi energy range of stability of the MgV^- configuration, according to ref 23. (h) Photoassisted transitions induced by 405 and 445 nm laser processing, involving the neutral charge state of the MgV defect.

Table 2. Fitting Parameters of the Wavelength-Dependent $I(E)$ Curves for the MgV^- ZPL Emission According to Equation 5

wavelength (nm)	I_0 (au)	a (au)	b (au)	α (J)	β (J)
520	32 ± 4			12 ± 3	
445	61 ± 9	44 ± 9	15 ± 5	19 ± 8	1.2 ± 0.6
405	66 ± 4	46 ± 4	13 ± 6	18 ± 5	0.4 ± 0.4

the MgV^{2-} . We can hypothesize that this level could be represented by the neutral charge configuration of the defect (MgV^0), although a definitive assessment would require further investigation. The ionization of the MgV^- center via one-photon absorption in the $E_i = 2.38 \rightarrow 2.79$ eV range determines a complementary (i.e., $E_{\text{gap}} - E_i = 2.71 \rightarrow 3.06$ eV photon energy range, see Figure 3h for a schematic representation) energy required for the reverse process that consists in the conversion of MgV^0 to MgV^- via the capture of valence-band electrons. The occurrence of both ionization and recombination between MgV^0 and MgV^- centers could thus explain the modest excitability of the MgV^- emission under laser wavelengths below 500 nm reported in previous works.¹⁹ It is finally worth remarking that the fitting value found for the α parameter with an energy scale of ~ 10 J is mutually compatible for all of the adopted processing wavelengths. Furthermore, the β parameter identified for the 445 and 405 nm describes the additional laser-induced interactions as a significantly faster process described by a ~ 1 J energy scale.

The time-dependent increase in the PL emission from Mg-implanted diamond was also investigated. Figure 4a shows the PL intensity during the laser processing over a 900 s time interval under a 522 nm wavelength at 5.3 mW optical power. The photon count rate was monitored using the same processing laser as PL excitation source in the sample. Furthermore, it is worth noting the difference due to the laser irradiation on the count traces acquired simultaneously with the photoactivation process. The count trace exhibits a monotonic increase in the PL emission intensity, indicating cumulative activation of MgV^- centers located within the confocal excitation spot. Notably, the PL increase features several discrete jumps between constant photon count rates, suggesting the separate activation of individual color centers. The obtained activation resulted to be fully irreversible for all of the explored laser processing conditions, as confirmed by the juxtaposition (Figure 4b,c) of two separate PL confocal maps acquired from the same region processed under a 405 nm laser at a 4 months time interval. The persistence of the PL features, which is in line with the comparable formation energy of the three considered charge states within the stability range of the MgV^- configuration,²³ guarantees a permanent activation of color centers at specific locations of the implanted samples, thus offering a viable tool for the direct writing (i.e., direct photoactivation) of single-photon emitters.

The observation of discrete jumps in the time-dependent PL emission during laser processing enabled us to assess whether the CW treatment was effective at producing individual MgV^- optical centers. An exemplary case is displayed in Figure 5 in the proximity of a spot processed for 10 h under the 445 nm

Figure 4. (a) Real-time MgV^- PL intensity under laser processing at 522 nm wavelength (5.3 mW optical power). (b, c) Confocal PL microscopy scans of the region processed with 405 nm laser. The maps were acquired under 522 nm laser excitation (100 μW optical power) (b) 1 h and (c) 4 months after the laser processing.

Figure 5. (a) PL map of a confocal spot in Mg-implanted diamond processed under 445 nm laser wavelength (5 mW) for 10 h, surrounded by process-induced diffraction-limited PL emitting features. (b) PL emission spectrum and second-order autocorrelation function acquired from the spot circled in white in (a). (c) MgV^- ZPL intensity and formation efficiency of the MgV^- center as a function of the laser processing wavelength and deposited energy. The tinted areas describe the 95% confidence bands.

laser wavelength (optical power: 5 mW). The corresponding PL map (Figure 5a, acquired under 522 nm probing laser excitation at 100 μW power) shows several diffraction-limited spots surrounding the irradiated spots, attributed to the spatial Gaussian profile of the processing laser. The emission spectrum as well as the background-subtracted second-order autocorrelation function $g^{(2)}(t)$ (reported in Figure 5b for the individual spot circled in white in Figure 5a) evidenced the occurrence of single-photon emitters with the spectral signature of the MgV^- center. The identification of individual emitters enabled quantifying the PL intensity I_s at the single center level, which was determined as the integral of the ZPL spectral peak intensity averaged over 5 different emitters. This value was used as a normalization factor to quantify the number N_1 of MgV^- emitters fabricated at each processed spot under the assumption of a linear scaling between the number of emitters and the PL emission intensity.

Considering the number N_i of Mg ions introduced by ion implantation in the confocal volume as the product between the implantation fluence $F = 1 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and the confocal spot size given by the diffraction limit ($A = 7 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{m}^2$), the N_1/N_i ratio value is a direct assessment of the MgV^- formation

efficiency for the process, defined as the number of optically active emitters per implanted ion. The calculated formation efficiency is plotted in Figure 5c for all of the considered processing wavelengths and deposited energies. The formation efficiency for the MgV^- center is thus lower bound to a $0.11 \pm 0.02\%$ value for the 522 nm processing wavelengths and to 0.16 ± 0.02 and $0.18 \pm 0.02\%$ values at 445 and 405 nm, respectively.

Sn-Related Centers. A similar characterization as the one reported for the MgV^- center was carried out for Sn-related color centers. The processing parameters were chosen according to the same experimental details as shown in Table 1. Although different intermediate values for the deposited energy were selected for the two implanted species, the observed trend ensures the analogy of the process. In Figure 6a–c, the arrays of spots processed at different laser processing wavelengths (namely, 522, 445, and 405 nm, respectively) are shown. Also in the case of the 595 nm Sn-related emission, processing by means of a 594 nm laser source did not result in any activation of the color center. In Figure 6d–f, the corresponding PL intensity curves (extracted as the integral area underlying the 593 nm ZPL emission) are plotted

Figure 6. Photoactivation dependence on the laser processing parameters for the Sn-related 595 nm color center. The first row shows the confocal maps acquired on an array of spots undergone photoactivation via laser processing at (a) 522 nm, (b) 445 nm, and (c) 405 nm. The second row shows the integrated PL intensity (integral of the 595 nm ZPL spectral peak) collected spots as a function of the energy deposited on each spot under processing wavelengths of (d) 522 nm, (e) 445 nm, and (f) 405 nm. (g) Spectrum acquired from a spot processed under a 405 nm laser at 30 J delivered energy.

Table 3. Fitting Parameter of the Wavelength-Dependent $I(E)$ Curves for the 595 nm Sn-Related PL Emission According to Equation 5

wavelength (nm)	I_0 (au)	a (au)	b (au)	α (J)	β (J)
520	5.1 ± 0.8			10 ± 3	
445	14.9 ± 1.2			15 ± 3	
405	24 ± 3	14 ± 3	8.7 ± 0.7	140 ± 50	0.8 ± 0.2

Figure 7. (a) PL map of a confocal spot in Sn-implanted diamond processed under 445 nm laser wavelength (5 mW) for 10 h, surrounded by process-induced diffraction-limited PL emitting features. (b) PL emission spectrum and second-order autocorrelation function acquired from the spot circled in white in (a). (c) 595 nm spectrum intensity and formation efficiency of the 595 nm center as a function of the laser processing wavelength and deposited energy. The tinted areas describe the 95% confidence bands.

versus the total energy deposited at each processing spot. The energy dependence shows a similar behavior with respect to what is discussed in eqs 1–5 and Figure 3d–f for the MgV^- center.

The curves were fitted according to the model described in eq 5 and showed a similar decrease in the asymptotic PL emission intensity at increasing wavelengths, indicating a

higher activation efficiency at higher processing photon energies. Differently from the results recorded for the MgV^- center, however, both the $I(E)$ curves corresponding to 522 and 445 nm laser processing could be suitably described with a single-exponential trend (i.e., $b = 0$ in eq 5), which is compatible with a photoactivation process involving the ionization of a single dark charge state into the optically

active 595 nm emission. Conversely, the fitting of the $I(E)$ curve acquired related to the 405 nm processing wavelength required the introduction of a second exponential term according to eq 5. Also, the resulting exponential damping parameters (all fitting parameters are reported in Table 3) were in this case significantly modified with respect to the case of the other processing wavelengths, exhibiting a dominant contribution (i.e., $\sim 60\%$ of the emission intensity through the parameter a in eq 5) from a process defined by $\alpha = 140 \pm 50$ J, paired with a second process described by $\beta = 0.8 \pm 0.2$ J. The need for a second exponential term could be together with an exhaustive description of the process would require a better understanding of the nature of the defect emitting at 595 nm. This emission was indeed reported in Sn-implanted diamond alongside the SnV^- ZPL,^{21,34} but its properties are largely unexplored at the state of the art. Despite the lack of specific studies available on the photophysical properties of this defect, Iwasaki et al.³⁴ hypothesized its attribution to a bond-centered defect in a different structural configuration with respect to the SnV^- center. This attribution is justified by the fact that the 595 nm optical center, differently from the SnV^- , anneals out at temperatures above 1400 °C.³⁴ This picture appears to be fully in line with the available structural analysis of the SnV^- center formation by emission channeling technique.³³

The interpretation of the 595 nm line as a different charge state of the SnV complex is further ruled out by the occasional activation of the SnV^- emission at 620 nm under the sole 405 nm laser processing (Figure 6g). The observation of both PL emission lines could justify the significant variation in the α parameter under 405 nm processing due to the emergence of two competing ionization processes.

Similarly to what was performed for the MgV^- optical center, several individual Sn-related emitters were identified in the processed spots. An exemplary result is shown in Figure 7a, where the PL map of the region surrounding a spot processed at 405 nm laser wavelength (900 J delivered energy) exhibits different isolated emitting spots that are diffraction-limited in size. The occurrence of single-photon emission from 595 nm centers (spectral signature shown in Figure 7b for the emitter circled in white in Figure 7a) was assessed by Hanbury-Brown & Twiss interferometry (Figure 7b), showing a $g^{(2)}(t = 0) = 0.21 \pm 0.03$ value under 80 μW probing laser excitation with a characteristic emission time of ~ 7.2 ns.

The formation efficiency was estimated using the same procedure adopted for the MgV^- center for the considered laser processing wavelengths. The analysis yielded asymptotic efficiency values of 4.25 ± 0.07 , 2.11 ± 0.04 , and $1.23 \pm 0.02\%$ for 405, 445, and 522 nm processing wavelengths, respectively, Figure 7c. It is worth remarking that the reported values, especially the one obtained under 405 nm irradiation, are satisfactorily compatible with what has been reported for other centers (SnV , MgV , GeV) under conventional ion irradiation and high-temperature postimplantation annealing.^{48–51}

DISCUSSION

In this work, the optical activation of the MgV^- and of the 595 nm Sn-related optical centers was demonstrated following ion implantation and laser processing with visible laser source at optical powers in the 1–25 mW range. The PL emission from these color centers was obtained without the need for conventional thermal treatments^{25–28} after ion implantation. The activation of the centers was correlated to the energy density delivered by the laser source on the processed spots

and was interpreted in terms of charge state conversion of the considered point defects. The occasional activation of the SnV^- center in Sn-implanted diamond was observed under 405 nm processing.

These findings, which are complementary with respect to what has been recently reported for laser-induced SiV^0 – SiV^- photodynamics,^{52,53} confirm that a fraction of the Mg- and Sn-related defects is found in the structural bond-centered configuration right after ion implantation, as already observed in previous studies.^{19,33} Conversely, the formation efficiency estimated for all the considered defect classes ($\sim 1\%$) suggests that other factors may affect the optical activation of structurally stable defects, such as the effect on the Fermi level local environment in implanted, radiation-damaged diamond.^{54,55}

Although rather low, the non-negligible formation efficiency associated with these laser-based processes enables us to identify a strategy for the controlled activation of quantum-light emitters in diamond by loosening the stringent requirements on single-ion implantation.^{56,57} First, in this work, it was shown that the ion implantation did not result in the appearance of background photons, since no detectable signal is observed right after ion implantation, and that the color centers activated by laser processing display a stable emission over months of probing time. Second, the activation was found to be spatially constrained to the focusing spot of the processing laser, and it was achieved by exploiting the same probing confocal microscope needed for the subsequent excitation and optical manipulation of the emitters. Third, the formation of individual emitters was directly monitored by detecting discrete increases in the PL emission count rate detected by the confocal microscope itself. Thus, a fabrication protocol can be devised, in which an adequate ion fluence (e.g., ~ 100 ions per implanted spot, according to the formation efficiency) is combined with the real-time, in situ laser processing technique to achieve the activation of individual color centers at specific positions of a large-area sample. However, the realization of these isolated single-photon sources through this protocol would require further investigation aimed at avoiding the potential activation of nearby competing emitters. A potential pathway toward this deterministic implementation would rely on the combination of the saturation behavior observed for the activation process with the identification of an optimal ion implantation fluence. Additionally, an improvement in the spatial accuracy in this protocol could be achieved using either submicrometric masking or focused ion beams, fostering the deterministic aspect of the technique.

The reported lithographic system, based on a confocal microscope, is simple and offers the advantage of spatial resolution with respect to conventional thermal annealing without requiring challenging focusing or collimation procedures for impinging ion implantation beam. Furthermore, the experimental apparatus is relatively inexpensive with respect to the exploitation of more elaborate laser sources (e.g., femtosecond lasers^{35–38}) relying on irreversible local structural modification and annealing of the host material.

METHODS

Sample Preparation. The measurements were conducted on two high-purity single-crystal IIa diamond substrates with $\langle 100 \rangle$ orientation, with a nominal concentration of both substitutional B and N dopants the < 5 ppb. Both samples were

implanted using the multielemental negative ion implanter of the Solid State Physics Laboratories of the University of Torino.^{58–60} A collimation system was used to define a ~millimeter-sized implantation area. The ion fluence was estimated by the exposure time of the sample to the ion beam and the relative ion current, which was measured on a Faraday cup prior and after the implantation. The sample did not undergo subsequent annealing and was thus laser processed without previous surface chemical functionalization steps or thermal annealing.

PL Confocal Microscopy. The PL characterization of color centers at both the ensemble and single emitter levels was performed using a custom single-photon sensitive confocal microscope. The setup was equipped with a 100× dry objective (0.9 NA). A set of fiber-coupled CW laser diodes (522, 445, and 405 nm wavelengths) was exploited to deliver optical excitation. The photon collection was provided by coupling a pair of free-running, commercial Silicon single-photon avalanche diodes (Si-SPADs) (0.1 kcps dark count rate, ~45 ns deadtime, detection efficiency of ~50% at 520 nm) to a fiber-fused multimode beamsplitter whose $\varnothing = 50 \mu\text{m}$ core was exploited as the pinhole of the confocal microscope. The Si-SPADs pair fed an FPGA time-tagger board to enable the acquisition of second-order autocorrelation measurements. A 550 nm long-pass dichroic mirror was employed to decouple the excitation photons from the PL signal. The spectral analysis of the PL emission was performed using a fiber-coupled SpectraPro HRS 300 spectrograph equipped with a PIXIS camera (0.2 nm resolution, 330–800 nm spectral range). The PL emission from both samples was acquired by exploiting a 550 nm dichroic mirror along with a long-pass filter at a 550 nm cutoff wavelength to filter out the laser excitation. For the sole spectral analysis carried out on the laser-processed spots in MgH⁻-implanted diamond, an additional 650 nm short-pass filter was employed to filter out the background PL originating from radiation-induced, photoactivated GR1 centers (see Supporting Information S4—GR1 center photoactivation).⁴⁵

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsphotonics.5c00826>.

PL count rate stability reported for the readout parameters for a period longer than the acquisition time, as a countercheck of the further activation of emitters in this specific condition; comparison between the diamond Raman peak of the laser processed and solely implanted region for the Sn case; discussion on the possible photoionization process; stability of the activated spots upon chemical functionalization analyzed through PL confocal analysis; and activation of the GR1 center in diamond upon CW laser irradiation for the case of Mg-ion irradiation (PDF)

■ AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

Elena Nieto Hernández – *Physics Department, University of Torino and Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN), 10125 Torino, Italy*; orcid.org/0000-0001-6216-9256; Email: elena.nietoherandez@unito.it

Authors

- Vanna Pugliese – *Physics Department, University of Torino and Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN), 10125 Torino, Italy*
- Emilio Corte – *Physics Department, University of Torino and Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN), 10125 Torino, Italy*
- Marco Govoni – *Department of Physics, Computer Science and Mathematics, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, 41125 Modena, Italy*
- Sviatoslav Ditalia Tchernij – *Physics Department, University of Torino and Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN), 10125 Torino, Italy*; orcid.org/0000-0002-2639-5229
- Paolo Olivero – *Physics Department, University of Torino and Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN), 10125 Torino, Italy*
- Jacopo Forneris – *Physics Department, University of Torino and Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN), 10125 Torino, Italy*

Complete contact information is available at:

<https://pubs.acs.org/10.1021/acsphotonics.5c00826>

Author Contributions

V.P., E.N.H., and J.F. designed the experiments and the characterization procedure. V.P., E.N.H., E.C., and S.D.T. defined the ion implantation procedure and performed the ion implantation. V.P., E.N.H., and E.C. performed laser irradiation and PL characterization experiments. V.P., J.F., M.G., and P.O. developed the interpretational model. S.D.T., E.C., E.N.H., and V.P. developed the confocal microscopy system and contributed to the PL analysis. V.P. and E.N.H. led PL analysis campaigns of samples and data processing. E.N.H., V.P., J.F., and P.O. prepared the original draft of the manuscript. All authors reviewed and edited the manuscript.

Notes

The work reported in this manuscript was submitted to the arXiv preprint server previous to publication in this journal; the associated paper can be found as follows: Pugliese, V.; Nieto Hernández, E.; Corte, E.; Govoni, M.; Ditalia Tchernij, S.; Olivero, P.; Forneris, J. Photoactivation of Color Centers Induced by Laser Irradiation in Ion-Implanted Diamond. 2024, arXiv:2409.06359. arXiv.org e-Print archive. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2409.06359> (accessed Sept 10th, 2024).

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

Recently, we became aware of other two studies presenting a similar protocol for the activation of NV color centers in diamond, making use of CW laser in the mW range.^{61,62}

■ ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the following projects: Project “Piemonte Quantum Enabling Technologies” (PiQuET), funded by the Piemonte Region within the “Infra-P” scheme (POR-FESR 2014–2020 program of the European Union); “Training on LASer fabrication and ION implantation of DEFects as quantum emitters” (LasIonDef) project, funded by the European Research Council under the “Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Networks” program; “Departments of Excellence” (L. 232/2016), funded by the Italian Ministry of Education, University and Research (MIUR); “Ex post funding of research—2021” of the University of Torino funded by the “Compagnia di San Paolo”; experiments ROUGE, QUISS funded by the fifth National Commission of the Italian

National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN). We acknowledge financial support under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), Mission 4, Component 2, Investment 1.1, Call for tender No. 1409 published on 14.9.2022 by the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR), funded by the European Union—NextGenerationEU—Project P2022KSTSR—Opto-mechanical effects in spin-defects for quantum technologies—CUP D53D23019370001 and CUP E53D23018400001. The project PNRR MUR project PE_00000023—SPOKE 4—CUP B53C22004170006 “Optospin”. The project contributing to this work 23NRM04 NoQTeS has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.”

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